

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

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Linguistic features of national craft terms in English and Uzbek languages

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Annotation. Linguistics is an independent and specific science of language, which studies the origin, historical development processes and laws of language on a scientific basis. This subject consists of specific and general linguistics. Linguistics is divided into microlinguistics and macrolinguistics. Microlinguistics studies only the internal, i.e. phonetic, lexical and grammatical structure of the language, while macrolinguistics combines language with other disciplines.

Key words: terminology, language, linguistic, features, specific

The "Fundamentals of Linguistics" course examines the main issues of language sciences, therefore, without having such knowledge, it is impossible to fully imagine some of its sections. The most basic problems investigated by the science of linguistics are studied in the science "Fundamentals of Linguistics". In addition to linguistics, language is also studied by other subjects such as philosophy and logic. Language is also studied by sociologists because of the connection between language and the development of society. Linguists also use materials and conclusions from such disciplines as history, ethnography, psychology, anthropology, mathematics, geography, and physics. It would not be wrong to say that the first steps in linguistics in the world were taken from the times when the need for communication between people was felt. The science of linguistics is one of the sciences with the longest history. It began to develop in Ancient India and

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Ancient Greece (Greece) a few hundred years ago. The issue of the existence of a connection between a word and its conceptual essence has been the cause of considerable debate among scientists and philosophers of ancient Greece. As a result of the analysis and observations, the initial theoretical ideas about the vocabulary of the language and the emergence of vocabulary were based on the results. In the first half of the 19th century, great achievements were made in the field of linguistics. In particular, in this period, a comparative-historical method was formed in linguistics, and in accordance with it, the science of language began to be called the science of comparative-historical linguistics. Realizing that European languages are closely related to Sanskrit (ancient Indian), the interrelationships of these languages began to be seriously studied. German scientists Franz Bopp (1791-1867), Jacob Grimm (1785-1863), Danish scientist Rasmus Rask (1787-1832), Russian scientist Alexander Vostokov (1781-1864), Czech scientist, especially in the comparative-historical study of languages. People like Dobrovsky (1753-1829) made great contributions. The interesting part is that these scientists, independently of each other and at the same time, met at one point to develop the method, idea and principles of comparative-historical study of languages.

Craftsman has been developed in the territory of Uzbekistan for a long times. This process served to improve not only people's life style, economics of the state but also local language of people who lived in this land. It was started to great desire to terms to use new notions in language because of etymology and creation of new types of craftsmanship. In this process people used two ways in solving the problem. Firstly, people created new terms in case of using the opportunities of

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local language. Secondly, they had to borrow many terms from other foreign languages. These processes served to enrich vocabulary of local language. The results of analyzing terms on handicraftsmanship used in Uzbek language vocabulary widely showed that words borrowed from Arabian and Persian languages have great amount in Uzbek language vocabulary. The reason of this is that people who lived in this land participated active in international trade from ancient time and the land became the trade center. It was paid great attention to this process in Temurid's period.

Trade caravans from different continents all over the world served to enrich our language with new words. Besides, because of bringing craftsmen from different countries by Amir Temur many new terms were borrowed into our language with new types of craftsmanship. Borrowed craft terms are the object of study of a number of researchers, they consider them from different angles, one of the leading applicants is F.Abaeva[5], B. Balzhinimaeva[6], I. Marghitsu[7], O. Trubachev[8], E. Danilova[9], E. Squire[10]. II. The notion of borrowed word. When a word comes into another language it adapts the phonetic, grammatical, lexical system of that language. This process is considered as the assimilation of a borrowed word. According to Thomason and Kaufman, the term borrowing has been used in two different senses: a) as a general term for all kinds of transfer or copying processes, whether they are due to native speakers adopting elements from other languages into the recipient language, or whether they result from nonnative speakers imposing properties of their native language onto a recipient language. This general sense seems to be by far the most prevalent use of the term borrowing. But borrowing has also been used in a more restricted sense, b) "to refer to the

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incorporation of foreign elements into the speakers' native language" [2, p.21] As L.P. Krysin mentioned borrowing is a process of moving various elements from one language to another. Under different elements are meant units of different levels of language structure, though phonology, morphology, syntax, vocabulary, semantics [4, p.270]. W. Weinreich in his article "Monolingualism and Multilingualism" (1972) says that "the dictionary of any language is constantly in a fluid state, some words are falling out of use, others, on the contrary, are being circulated. Due to the ease of spreading lexical units (in comparison with phonological and grammatical rules), a minimal contact between languages is sufficient for borrowing words" [4, p.70]. The degree of assimilation of borrowings depends on the following factors: a) from what group of languages the word was borrowed, if the word belongs to the same group of languages to which the borrowing language belongs it is assimilated easier, b) in what way the word is borrowed: orally or in the written form, words borrowed orally are assimilated quicker, c) how often the borrowing is used in the language, the greater the frequency of its usage, the quicker it is assimilated, d) how long the word lives in the language, the longer it lives, the more assimilated it is. III. Lexical layer of Uzbek craftsmanship terminology We can see many borrowed terms in the lexical layer of terminology on craftsmanship. The usage of Arabian and Persian languages in economical, commercial, science, literature and art spheres effected to the development of terminological system of craftsmanship. Words borrowed from Arabian and Persian languages adopted in Uzbek language strictly and as a result, we can identify the etymology of these words only according to the explanatory and etymological dictionaries. [1, p.67] Uzbek language enriched on the basis of

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borrowing words from other languages and new words were created from these borrowed words on the basis of inner opportunities of Uzbek language. As a result these new terms have been implemented to people's communication.

Conclusion From the above mentioned examples, we can see that the Uzbek craftsmanship terms belong not only to the Uzbek language, but also to Arabic, Persian and other foreign languages. The main reason of this is that Uzbek land became important trade centers, skilled craftsmanship brought from different foreign countries, all fields of craftsmanship were improved in Uzbek land from ancient times.

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реестр:1070589

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